

AN INQUIRY INTO THE EFFECTS OF CULTURAL INTELLIGENCE ON BIBLICAL PREACHING IN AFRICAN CHURCHES*

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Abstract

The multicultural nature and diversity of contemporary African churches challenge Christian preaching. From general observation, some African preachers seem to have yet come to that reality, consequently in how they present their sermons they portray either a lack of knowledge or an application of cultural hermeneutics. Given this cultural awareness, the paper inquires into the effects of cultural intelligence on Christian/biblical preaching in African churches. The paper reveals that preaching is a cultural activity, and for Christ to transform cultures, including African cultures, preachers must desist from being culturally biased and embrace the application of cultural intelligence. The paper adopts an analytical approach. Other findings on the effects of cultural intelligence on preaching include promoting a coherent understanding of sermons, helping to retain sermons, and promoting significant positive responses to sermons, among others. The paper encourages African preachers to be more intentional in maximising the application of cultural intelligence for efficacious preaching.

Keywords: Preaching, Culture, Sermon, Cultural hermeneutics, and Congregation.

Introduction

The imperative of cultural intelligence in Christian preaching for implementing the Great Commission of Jesus Christ given to the church cannot be overemphasised. The reason is because the Commission is to all nations in their varied cultural affiliations, including the African society. Whereas some contemporary gospel preachers in Africa have jettisoned cultural intelligence based on how they present their sermons in the

* Citation for this article as published: Emmanuel Akande Owoeye, "An Inquiry into the Effects of Cultural Intelligence on Biblical Preaching in African Churches." *Journal of the African Homiletics Society*, Volume 1, 2024, 200 – 214. ISSN – 3043–6257. <https://africanhomileticsociety.org/resources.php?id=12>

recent past, Dreyer notes that “A new scenario is currently unfolding, namely that churches are increasingly being confronted with the phenomenon of multiculturalism and diversity at a local level.”¹ Therefore, cultural intelligence has become necessary for African preachers in current times. The statement implies that for effective Christian preaching at the local congregational level, the gospel preachers must rise to the multicultural reality of their congregations.

The paper investigates the effects of cultural intelligence on biblical preaching in African churches. The purpose is to argue that cultural intelligence significantly influences gospel preaching in the present local churches in Africa. The paper encourages preachers to intentionally maximise the application of cultural intelligence for efficacious biblical preaching. The paper begins with a discussion on the conceptualisation of preaching and its contextualisation; it will then examine preaching and cultural intelligence. It further discusses the effects of cultural intelligence on preaching before the conclusion.

Conceptualisation of Preaching and its Contextualisation

The attention of this section is to discuss the conceptualisation of preaching and its need for contextualisation. It will also shed light on the level or forms of relationship between Christ and culture in the light of biblical preaching. Various scholars from various perspectives have defined preaching. However, the paper adopts David W. Augsburger and Mitties M. DeChamplain’s definition, “Preaching is a cultural event. No sermon is a-cultural, apolitical, asexual, a-economic, or a-racial. Every sermon occurs in a complex of cultural diversity with contrasting values on family, individual, age, gender, race, community”² A critical look at this definition draws two

implications. First, preaching originates from a culture and is communicated from a culture to another. It is never a-cultural. Second, it is cross-cultural as it addresses a complex of cultural diversity. “All preaching is cross-cultural as it seeks to bring the multiple strange worlds of the Bible and Christian heritage to bear on our own.”³ It is an interaction between the culture of the biblical world and the relevance of the message to the world and cultures of the audience. This definition, therefore, maintains that biblical preaching is a cross-cultural interaction of the message between the Bible world and the world of the audience.

Furthermore, Dreyer maintains that preaching bears the challenge of allowing the dynamic contents of the happenings of transculturation to grow in the new cultural seedbed of its audience. It does not involve divesting the biblical message of its cultural cloak.⁴ Invariably, preaching has to be contextual. Ezekiel Ajibade defines contextualisation as “Planting, watering, and nurturing the gospel message within the culture so much that people feel a sense of ownership of it and are ready to run with it without tampering with the biblical roots and essence of the message.”⁵ Contextual preaching in Africa, the writer’s origin, involves making the message biblical, then African, so that it is faithful to the inspired word but incarnated in the culture of Africans.⁶

Therefore, notwithstanding the varied cultural realities of the African people, biblical preaching should be contextual. Some of these realities include using folks, tales, and proverbs, among others, in effective language communication. V. S. Dada, corroborating Ajibade, asserts that the message, the messenger, and the audience are three critical factors for effective biblical preaching. According to Dada, the audience is the most significant of the three factors because they are the reason for the message

and the messenger.⁷ For the writer, however, all three factors are germane because each factor plays a critical role and depends on one another. Hence, an effective gospel preacher should be concerned about having little knowledge of the audience to assist in his orality; just as Ajibade submits, “Orality remains a very potent attempt toward reaching the world for Christ in a holistic and time efficient manner.”⁸

On this note, since the knowledge of the audience is essential in preparing the preacher, advancing a glimpse into a few realities in African churches becomes germane. An overview of African realities is that culture plays essential roles in their foundation and expressions, including in their churches. Discussing the peculiarities of African churches, Stephen V. Coertze and other writers enumerate specific characteristics in African churches: first, emphasis is placed on community rather than on the individual;⁹ second, salvation and healing are gifts that God gives to his people here and now.¹⁰ Third, the focus is on this life rather than the next. Fourth, as part of their heritage, Africans have always been aware of the world of spirits. The African church can identify a variety of spirits.¹¹ Others include singing in worship and promotion of unity in all activities, among others.¹²

Invariably, while affirming that preaching is contextual, it is worth noting that there is a contention about the relationship that should exist between Christ (and Christianity) and culture. Some argued that there is confusion between the meaning of culture and metanarrative because they opine that no significant explanation makes sense of all the little stories of the gospel. The arguments agree with one of the propositions of postmodernists: the affirmation of the death of the metanarrative.¹³ The other argument holds that discussions between Christ and culture are incoherent because all forms of Christianity are inherently and unavoidably embedded in cultural

expression.¹⁴ How, then, can there be a dialogue with only one partner? Before delving into that argument, advancing a definition and discussion on culture is crucial. Culture is “The set of attitudes, values, beliefs, and behaviours shared by a group of people, but different for each individual, communicated from one generation to the next.”¹⁵ The definition implies that culture entails virtually everything about a people group passed down from various generations.

Consequent to the preceding and the challenge of preaching Christ to the contemporary African world of pluralistic ideologies, necessity demands shedding light on one of the earlier-mentioned arguments: Christ and culture are incoherent because all forms of Christianity are inherently and unavoidably embedded in cultural expression. At first, the argument resulted from the rise of science and technology (the Enlightenment) in the Western world, which led to a drastic turn away from the Christian culture that has shaped the world for centuries.¹⁶ The world became hostile to Christianity and could only tolerate it, provided it was entirely private. Carson, describing the ugly situation, asserts, “All of us who live in large urban centres necessarily interact nowadays with Hindus, Sikhs, and even animists, as well as with secularists. As the new slogan says, ‘Nobody is leaving anyone alone and isn’t ever again going to. The multiplicity of religious claims is here to stay, and governments are going to have to get used to it.’”¹⁷ Invariably, the rising hostility leads to the rejection of the Christian culture, and every religious ideology seeks recognition and assertion of its cultural philosophies.

To this challenge, the response of Christians varied. A few advocated one form of withdrawal or the other; others sought to gain more access to the media. Nevertheless, other groups advanced valiant efforts to influence the government to pass

appropriate legislation. Another school of thought, consciously or unconsciously, developed a two-tier perception, one for the church or Christ and the other for broader cultural encounters. The premise of these responses initiated the argument seeking to address the relationship between Christ and culture. Hence, it is worth mentioning that Carson explained Richard Niebuhr's five paradigms concerning the relationship between Christ and culture. However, the paper focuses on the fifth, Christ, the transformer of culture.¹⁸ According to Carson's explanation of Niebuhr, Jesus Christ should be taught and presented as the transformer of culture, not otherwise. Carson's allusion to Niebuhr's paradigm on the relationship between Christ and culture and the understanding that Christ relates to culture with a view of transformation makes it essential for preachers not only to possess the knowledge of cultures but also to be culturally intelligent. On this note, the need arises for discussion on cultural intelligence.

Preaching and Cultural Intelligence

As a sequel to the previous discussion establishing preaching as a cultural activity that must be contextual, the need arises to advance discussion on the skills to aid effective preaching that is contextualised. The skill, therefore, is cultural intelligence. According to Matthew D. Kim, cultural intelligence is "the capability to deal effectively with other people with whom the person does not share a common cultural background and understanding."¹⁹ A cogent point from the definition is that cultural intelligence involves dealing effectively with people from different cultural backgrounds and understanding. This dealing is also critical because biblical preaching, as earlier affirmed, as a cultural event is cross-cultural. Therefore, imbibing the skill of cultural

intelligence is very germane to preachers if they seek effectiveness in the discharge of their assignment.

Using Livermore's four stages of cultural intelligence, Kim implores preachers to familiarise themselves and develop the skills in all the stages they can adapt for their homiletical purposes. The paper gives a brief discussion of the four stages. The first stage is the drive for cultural intelligence, a level of interest, drive, and energy to adapt cross-culturally.²⁰ At this stage, the preacher possesses an inner longing to understand similar and dissimilar congregants better. For African churches, the preacher develops an interest in acquainting with each member of the congregation. The love for the congregation requires getting to know them beyond their names and professions; the preacher knows each by who they are, what culture and subcultures they identify with, their dreams and fears, and the beliefs they hold closely, among others.

The second stage of cultural intelligence is knowledge. This stage refers to the knowledge of the preacher about culture and the role it plays in shaping how preaching is done.²¹ The knowledge of assessing how similar and different cultures shape human thinking and behaviour helps preachers prepare their sermons adequately. For instance, what knowledge does the preacher have about various listeners as he prepares to preach to them? What influences their daily decisions, their individualistic or collective preferences, and the values they treasure, among others?

The third stage is strategy. The strategy stage, or metacognitive intelligence, refers to the ability of the preacher to strategise when crossing cultures.²² According to Kim, the strategy involves three things, namely, the awareness of what is going on within oneself and others; taking time to plan for a cross-cultural encounter – anticipating how to approach the people, topic, and situation; and lastly, monitoring

one's interactions to see if one's plan and expectations were appropriate. In the awareness aspect of strategising, Wong corroborates, "Both an 'exegesis of the self and personal questions on the 'personal socialisation of the Preacher' are important tools for preaching in a multicultural world."²³ By that, he enjoins preachers to be culturally self-reflective because many preachers with a pastoral heart tend to focus on the ministry to the congregation rather than carry out much self-reflection.

The fourth and final stage of cultural intelligence is action. The stage is the behavioural dimension in which the preacher demonstrates all three stages earlier mentioned. It involves the ability to act appropriately (verbal actions, non-verbal actions, speech acts, and using precise and accurate words and phrases when communicating specific types of messages) in a range of cross-cultural situations.²⁴ Hence, when a preacher applies all the first three stages, the sermon connects with the audience and the congregation. An awareness of the stages of cultural intelligence has a significant influence on preaching. The next section of the paper examines this in light of its effects on preaching.

Effects of Cultural Intelligence on Preaching in African Churches

This section discusses the effects of cultural intelligence on preaching among African churches. They are as follows.

Promotes a Coherent Understanding of Sermon

Cultural intelligence in preaching promotes a coherent understanding of the sermon. When a preacher engages in contextual orality in gospel communication, the audience will be carried along and understand what the sermon entails or addresses.²⁵ Since preachers are responsible for engaging in biblical interpretation as a cultural activity,

necessity demands that they possess cultural hermeneutics. “Cultural hermeneutics is the intentional use of cultural contexts, both of text and the contemporary reader [the audience], in the interpretive process.”²⁶ What Organ is affirming here is that a preacher should be deliberate in using cultural language and the context of the sermon's delivery. One important tool is the appropriate use of language. Allen observes that language shapes how humans think, feel, and act. From the basic ‘master story’ of a culture or community to the tiniest metaphor, language results in societal attitudes, behaviours, roles, and structures.²⁷

Helps the Audience to Retain the Sermon

Cultural intelligence helps the audience to retain the sermon. Findings from the author’s inquiry affirm that the use of relevant illustrations in the forms of poems, stories, and parables from the locality of the audience aids in the retention of sermons.²⁸

Deborah Organ also buttresses this assertion when she opines that many preachers have recognised that they interpret and preach through their cultural lens and that the Word of God truly comes alive for congregations when it is preached in their cultural idioms interpreted from within their specific cultural contexts.²⁹ To this end, preaching involves the act of bridge-building or bridge-crossing from the biblical world of the text to the cultures of the audience. An everyday reality among African people is that they appreciate stories, poems, proverbs, and the like. Engaging their use in biblical preaching delivery will help the preacher communicate his message into the hearts of the audience.

Motivates Attentiveness and Love for the Preacher’s Message

Cultural intelligence motivates congregants from various cultural affinities to be open to and love listening to the sermons of such a preacher. As earlier affirmed, the

multicultural reality of contemporary African churches should prompt the Christian preacher to strive to be understood by other congregants different from his cultural affinity. This position Helen Spencer-Oatey buttresses in her discussion on the characteristics of a culture. She advances twelve interrelated vital characteristics, but only one is relevant here: “Culture is manifested at different layers of depth.”³⁰ By that, Spencer-Oatey opines that there are three levels at which culture manifests: (i) Through visual artefacts, which include things from the physical outlook such as dress code, manner of addressing one another, smell and appearance. (ii) Through the values expressed in the behaviours. The domains of values may either be ultimate or debatable. (iii) Basic assumptions are coined within/coded in the values. With this point, though culture manifests in different layers when a preacher takes advantage of the awareness of cultural manifestations and applies it in their sermon delivery, audiences from another cultural affinity would be endeared to listening to their sermon.

Encourages Positive Responses to Sermon

Cultural intelligence spurs significant positive responses from the congregants to sermons when the preacher connects to the realities of the people. Leonora Tisdale asserts that intentionally contextual preaching involves giving equally serious attention to the interpretation of congregations and their sociocultural contexts.³¹ The preacher should use the sermon as a bridge-builder to connect with the realities of the congregation. In his discussion, John R. Stott considers preaching as bridge-building and enjoins preachers to handle boldly the major themes of human life, preach Christ with the ethical implications, and preach on social and political issues, among several others,³² as they relate to the people (audience of a preacher). In addition, since a preacher preaches to a multicultural congregation, the knowledge of cultural

differences from both universal human nature and unique individual personality would play a significant role in spurring a positive response if employed. As the name implies, universal human refers to what is generally common to all human beings irrespective of geographical location. It entails expressing feelings like anger, love, joy, sadness, and longing for relationships, among others.³³

Promotes Cordial Relationship with Preacher

Cultural intelligence helps a preacher demonstrate an intimate relationship with the congregation, which usually influences their response to sermons. This point dovetails the preceding in that the other aspect of cultural differentiation is the unique individual personality. The unique individual personality in culture addresses the unique mental programs an individual does not share with other human beings, traits partly inherited in the genes and learned through modification of experiences.³⁴ The interest a preacher demonstrates to members of his congregation in sharing their vision, struggles, pain, challenges, and successes will surely pull the members to the preachers. When they experience genuine care and love from the preacher, they will be bound to respond positively to his sermons.

Prevents Membership Loss in a Multi-cultural Church

Cultural intelligence also helps curtail membership loss in a multicultural and diverse urban church setting. This effect resulted from the response to a research questionnaire carried out by the writer. 92.3% of fifty-two respondents affirm that a preacher who appropriately connects with the congregation culturally would rarely lose membership due to cultural issues.³⁵ Rick Richardson sheds light on the issue by advancing seven principles that help to preach in a cross-cultural context.³⁶ Six of the principles are (i) honouring what the people honour; (ii) using the language with authenticity, if

possible, communicating personal awareness of the trust issues between cultures; (iii) using stories as a narrative theologian; (iv) focus on the preaching proper; (v) avoid judging the people's response from personal cultural cues; and (vi) being a lifelong learner by deliberate interest in other people groups. Considering the richness of these principles, if adequately applied by a preacher, they will help curtail the loss of membership.

Conclusion

The paper investigated the effects of cultural intelligence on preaching in African churches. It has affirmed that preaching is a cultural activity and must be contextual to be meaningful and impactful, especially in the contemporary multicultural African world with pluralistic ideology. More so, the four stages of cultural intelligence, namely, the drive, knowledge, strategy, and action discussed, remain crucial for preachers for their sermons to be efficacious. Therefore, the paper concludes that cultural intelligence significantly affects preaching in Africa Churches. Some of the positive effects include it spurs people to love listening to a preacher, encourages retention of the sermons, and motivates significant positive responses to a sermon, among others. Hence, the writer encourages preachers to be more intentional in applying cultural intelligence for efficacious preaching.

Consequently, it is necessary to make the following recommendations. First, preachers of the gospel must face the reality of the multicultural nature of their audience, irrespective of the location of the sermon, particularly among African congregations. Second, for effective biblical orality, preachers must intentionally engage cultural hermeneutics in preparing and delivering their sermons. Third, the

knowledge of Christ as the transformer of cultures should motivate preachers to desist from using their sermons to condemn different cultural ideologies or elevate one culture over the other. Fourth, gospel preachers are encouraged to be deliberate in developing cultural intelligence skills for impactful preaching.

Endnotes

¹ T. F. J. Dreyer, “Preaching and Culture” *HTS* 61, No. 3 (2005), 794.

² David W. Augsburger and Mitties McDonald DeChamplain, “Cross-Cultural Preaching” *Concise Encyclopedia of Preaching*, William H. William and Richard Lischer, eds. (Louisville: Westminster John Knox Press, 1995), 95 – 96.

³ Augsburger and DeChamplain, 96.

⁴ Dreyer, 800.

⁵ Ezekiel A. Ajibade, *Expository Preaching in Africa: Engaging Orality for Effective Proclamation*, (Buruku: Hippo Books, 2021), 2.

⁶ Ajibade, 2.

⁷ V.S.A. Dada, “Preparation and Delivery of Revival Sermons.” *Living & Preaching the Gospel*, Emiola Nihinlola and Folashade Oloyede, eds. (Ogbomoso: Publishing Unit, The Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, 2019), 51.

⁸ Ezekiel A. Ajibade, “Engaging Orality for Effective Christian Teaching or Preaching” *The Dynamics of Competent Gospel Ministry: Ministry Enrichment Series*, Volume 4, Emiola Nihinlola and Folashade Oloyede, eds. (Ogbomoso: NBTS Publishing Unit, 2019), 254.

⁹ Stephen Victor Coertze, “Challenges Facing the African Church: South African Theologians Speak Out” (Master Dissertation, University of Pretoria, South Africa, 2005), 28

¹⁰ N. H. Ngada, & K. E. Mofokeng, *African Christian Witness*. (Pietermaritzburg: Cluster Publications, 2001), 15.

¹¹ Ngada and Mofokeng, 23.

¹² Coertze, 29 – 32.

¹³ The problem with the death of the metanarrative is that Christianity is meaningless apart from the gospel—which is most certainly a metanarrative. Indeed, the Christian gospel is nothing more than one of the metanarrative. It, therefore, means that Christianity must surrender the truth that the gospel message is universally true and objectively established. On the contrary, Christianity is the excellent metanarrative of redemption. The story begins with creation by the sovereign, omnipotent God and continues through the fall of man into sin and the redemption of all sinners through the substitutionary work of Jesus Christ on the cross and miraculous resurrection from death. That resurrection account remains the only of its kind since the world's existence. (See, James W. Sire, *The Universe Next Door*, Fifth Edition, (Downer Groove: IVP Academic, 2009), 216).

¹⁴ D. A. Carson, “How to Think about Culture: Reminding Ourselves of Niebuhr,” *Christ and Culture Revisited*, (Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2012), e-copy.

¹⁵ D. Matsumoto, *Culture and Psychology*, (Pacific Grove, CA: Brooks/Cole, 1996), 16. Cited by Helen Spencer-Oatey, *What is culture? A Compilation of Quotations*. Global PAD Core Concepts. Available at Global PAD Open House, H. 2012, 2. <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/al/globalpad/interculturalskills/> accessed October 28, 2022.

¹⁶ The writer depends heavily on Carson to discuss the arguments in its briefest form (See, D. A. Carson, “How to Think about Culture: Reminding Ourselves of Niebuhr,” *Christ and Culture Revisited*, (Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans Publishing Company, 2012), e-copy

¹⁷ Carson.

¹⁸ The first four are: one, Christ is against culture; two is the Christ of culture; three is Christ is above culture; and four, Christ and culture in paradox. See Carson, for detailed discussion on these paradigms.

¹⁹ Matthew D. Kim, *Preaching with Cultural Intelligence: Understanding the People who hear our Sermons*. (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2017), 20. Citing, P. Christopher Earley and Soon Ang, *Cultural Intelligence: Individual Interactions Across Cultures*, (Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 2003), 12.

²⁰ Kim, 21. Citing David A. Livermore, *Cultural Intelligence: Improving Your CQ to Engage Our Multicultural World*, (Grand Rapids: Baker Academic, 2009), 26.

²¹ Kim, 22.

²² Kim, 22. Citing Livermore, 27.

²³ Daniel L. Wong, “Preaching in a Multicultural World,” 2. <https://www.preaching.com/articles/preaching-in-a-multicultural-world/> (accessed September 5, 2022).

²⁴ Kim, 23. Citing Livermore, 28.

²⁵ Ezekiel A. Ajibade, *Contextualization of Expository Preaching: Engaging Orality for Effective Proclamation in Africa*, (Ibadan: Baptist Press (Nig.) Ltd.), 69.

²⁶ Deborah A. Organ, “Cultural Hermeneutics” *The New Interpreter’s Handbook of Preaching*, Paul Scott Wilson, ed. (Nashville: Abindon Press, 2008), 143.

²⁷ Ronald J. Allen, “The Societal Function of Language in Preaching” (e-copy) <https://www.religion-online.org/book-chapter/chapter-5-the-social-function-of-language-in-preaching-by-ronald-j-allen/> Accessed September 9, 2022)

²⁸ In the study, 98% of fifty-two respondents affirmed the statement against 2% who disagreed to the statement. (Emmanuel A. Owoeye, “An Appraisal of the Effect of Cultural Intelligence on Preaching in a Local Church.” (Seminar Paper, Nigerian Baptist Theological Seminary, Ogbomoso, 2022), 10).

²⁹ Organ, 144.

³⁰ For the twelve characteristics of culture, please see, Helen Spencer-Oatey, *What is culture? A Compilation of Quotations*. Global PAD Core Concepts. Available at Global PAD Open House, H. 2012, 3–15 <http://www2.warwick.ac.uk/fac/soc/al/globalpad/interculturalskills/> (accessed October 28, 2022).

³¹ Leonora Tubbs Tisdale, *Preaching as Local Theology and Folk Art*, (Minneapolis: Fortress Press, 1997), 47.

³² John R. Stott, *Between Two Worlds: The Art of Preaching in the Twentieth Century*, (Grand Rapids: William B. Eerdmans’ Publishing Company, 1982), 138–159.

³³ Spencer-Oatey, 6.

³⁴ Spencer-Oatey, 6.

³⁵ Owoeye, 11.

³⁶ Rick Richardson, “Cross-Cultural Preaching: How to Connect in our Multicultural World” *Art and Craft of Biblical Preaching: A Comprehensive Resource for Today’s Commentators*, (Grand Rapids: Christianity Today International, 2005), 171–174.